
Exploring the Nature of Science through Data and Connections: Introducing Historical Network Analysis in Brazilian High School Physics Education

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Abstract

This paper presents an innovative educational approach integrating Historical Network Research (HNR) into Brazilian high school Physics education. The methodology focuses on fostering students' understanding of the Nature of Science (NOS) by leveraging the concept of Creating Historical Networks (CHN) (Alcantara, Braga, & van den Heuvel, 2020) and utilising tools such as ePistolarium and Gephi to visualise and analyse knowledge circulation in history of science. Activities are designed to actively involve students (ages 15–16) in collaborative research, encouraging critical evaluation of sources and network construction. The educational approach draws on Khishfe's (2023) review of NOS instruction frameworks, particularly integrating historical contexts to improve student comprehension of NOS aspects, such as cultural embedding and the circulation of knowledge and practices. The activities involve creating networks that highlight interactions between human and non-human actors, focusing on historical cases such as the dissemination of optical instruments in the Dutch Republic, the development of steam engines in England, the evolution of astronomical technologies for non-visible frequencies, and the Bernoulli's principles in fluid dynamics. Students are introduced to network concepts like nodes, links, hubs, weak ties, and ego networks, linking these to broader historical and epistemological discussions. The project also aligns with van den Heuvel et al. (2020) exploration of HNR methodologies as interactive and associative interfaces, demonstrating how network analysis tools can make complex historical data accessible to students. By modelling networks and interacting with incomplete historical datasets, students gain insights into the dynamics of knowledge production and dissemination in early modern science. These tools enable visual and conceptual understanding, bridging gaps between historical narratives and scientific inquiry. Preliminary findings suggest that CHN-based activities significantly enhance student engagement and critical thinking, offering new perspectives on the relationships between science, culture, and technology. However, challenges include ensuring methodological rigour and supporting students' independent research capabilities. This work contributes to the discourse on innovative pedagogical applications of HNR, illustrating its potential to enrich science education by embedding NOS instruction within historical and network-based contexts.

References

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